

SUPPORTING DATA FOR THE FOLLOWING PAPER PUBLISHED
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**Effects of increasing dietary inclusion of high oleic acid soybeans on milk
production of high-producing dairy cows**

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INTERPRETIVE SUMMARY

Increasing dietary inclusion of high oleic acid soybeans increases milk production of high-producing dairy cows. *By Bales et al., page XXX.* The objective of our study was to determine the effects of increasing dietary inclusion of roasted and ground high oleic acid soybean (HOSB) at 0, 8, 16, and 24% dry matter (DM) in high-producing, mid-lactation dairy cows. Increasing HOSB inclusion linearly decreased DM intake but increased yield of milk and milk components. Additionally, increasing HOSB inclusion linearly reduced de novo and mixed fatty acid yields but increased preformed milk fatty acid yield. Increasing HOSB inclusion tended to decrease plasma insulin concentration, but inclusion level did not affect body weight change. Increasing HOSB inclusion decreased urea nitrogen in milk and blood. Overall, increasing HOSB inclusion increased milk production responses of high-producing dairy cows.

Supplemental Table S1. Protein supply predictions from NASEM (2021) model¹

Variable	Treatment ²			
	0%	8%	16%	24%
RUP, %CP ³	35.6	40.2	45.5	53.7
RDP, %CP ⁴	64.4	59.8	54.5	46.3
RDP – Microbial Protein Balance, g/d	1432	1205	1011	750
RUP, g/d	1701	1978	2191	2626
Metabolizable Protein (MP) Supply, kg/d	3.03	3.23	3.27	3.47
MP from Microbes, kg/d	1.63	1.59	1.46	1.29
MP from RUP, kg/d	1.39	1.63	1.81	2.18
Dietary MP Supply, g/d	3027	3223	3275	3473
Predicted Supply of Lysine, g/d	225	237	237	245
Predicted Metabolizable AA Efficiency of Lysine	0.76	0.74	0.74	0.73
Predicted supply of Methionine, g/d	81	83	81	82
Predicted Metabolizable AA Efficiency of Methionine	0.68	0.68	0.69	0.70
EAA	1518	1608	1621	1702
NEAA	2670	2851	2903	3098

¹Estimated predictions based on NASEM (2021) software using data from Table 1 and Table 2 in the current study to reflect cow performance during the experiment.

²Inclusion level of HOSB, %DM

³Adapted from diet summary report from NASEM (2021) model output using equation: $([RUP, \%DM]/[CP, \%DM]) \times 100$.

⁴Adapted from diet summary report from NASEM (2021) model output using equation: $([RDP, \%DM]/[CP, \%DM]) \times 100$.